

Personnel Competencies in the Field of Tourism Personnel Management

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Abstract: Objective. In this paper has been analyzed personnel competencies in the field of tourism personnel management. By the author has been described the content of the competency-based approach from the point of view of the specific characteristics of employees in the tourism sector. In addition, this article analyzes the general classification of competencies, on the basis of which a model for the formation of universal competencies of tourism employees has been developed.

The purpose of the study is to create a model for the formation of universal competencies of employees at tourism enterprises.

Methods.

The study was carried out on the basis of content analysis of scientific works and methods devoted to the problems of forming and assessing universal competencies in tourism enterprises.

Results.

The formation of universal competencies for work in the field of tourism should be carried out on a systematic basis, starting from various levels of the education system, and supplemented with current practices integrated in the process of advanced training and retraining.

Conclusions.

The most effective model for the formation of universal competencies of tourism personnel will be implemented in the context of network interaction with the involvement of interested business entities and management of the tourism and recreational complex. Practice-oriented experience, transformed by specialists in the process of scientific and teaching activities, conducting master classes and professional tests with students studying in the areas of economics and management in the field of tourism, will be useful.

Keywords: Tourism, practice-oriented experience, specialists, infrastructure, transport, logistics, quality, tourism products.

1. Introduction

In the world, the tourism sector is directly related to the development of all infrastructures It is embodied as a socio-economic phenomenon that has an indirect effect. Modern tourism is the top of the transport, social and service sectors Based on the level of development, it is ultimately the economy

Tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan from the first days of our independence state support of the field, engaged in this field to create incentives for enterprises, as well as for the tourism sector Work on the formation of infrastructure continues at a rapid pace is being done.

It should be noted that on October 4, 1993, Uzbekistan became the World became the first member of the tourism organization among Central Asian countries. This in turn, it is very positive for the development of international tourism in Uzbekistan gave an impetus.

The tourism sector generates beneficial effects associated with its effective functioning. As a result of successfully operating enterprises, service innovations develop, new types of professional activities arise, and the quality of life of the population of host territories improves due to the growth of tourist flows and stimulation of job creation.

2. Literature review

The pandemic that began in 2020 has transformed organizational and managerial approaches to doing business. Significant changes were associated with restrictions on movement and cessation of activity in many areas of the economy. As a result, the service sector suffered significant losses; measures of state and regional support were required. The income of the hotel business, retail trade, tourism and excursion activities, catering, exhibition halls, passenger transport, tour operators and travel agencies decreased significantly (Tymoshenko, 2020). The most negative impact factor was interregional barriers to movement and the closure of transport corridors. Many tourism market entities were forced to close, and a negative trend of reduction in the number of enterprises emerged.

The recovery of the industry should be carried out not only on the basis of the development of infrastructure, transport, logistics and quality tourism products, but also the development of human resources (Bey, 2018). In the context of digitalization and the influence of technology on data exchange and communication with consumers, the universal skills of tourism enterprise specialists are of particular importance (Kapse, Patil, Patil, 2012). Qualified personnel play an important role in providing quality services in the industry.

The issue of providing qualified personnel in the tourism sector is relevant for our country. This is due to the dynamic development of this industry within the country, which requires a large number of diverse specialists. The tourism industry itself also facilitates the employment of various categories of the population without special education to engage in a very wide range of areas of this activity, and contributes to the filling of a large number of employees with non-core education (Bitter, 2020).

Qualified specialists in the field of tourism must have a set of specific digital competencies, functionally at all stages of the provision of tourism services (Gupta, Fernandes, Jain, 2018). This is a key factor in achieving the desired results for tourism businesses and should be the basis for the design of training and workforce development programs.

3. Analysis and results

There are such competencies as key and universal for carrying out professional activities in various aspects. These abilities are of paramount importance for performing work activities in certain conditions.

The problem of the formation and development of universal competencies is related to personnel training at the educational level. For example, an employee with a certain level of specialization may be influenced by new requirements for professional skills under the influence of scientific and technological progress and production organization technologies (Moshkin, 2016).

Universal competencies are a significant tool for the universalization of an employee, as well as readiness for self-realization and self-development.

Here are some interpretations of universal competence in scientific works:

- A high degree of adaptation and mobility of a specialist in solving constantly emerging professional

problems, based on the constant progress of abilities;

- The ability to implement theoretical knowledge when performing practical professional tasks, based on reflexive, analytical, situational thinking, which is important for many types of work in the field of tourism (Skulmovskaya, 2017).

It seems that universal competencies should be understood as the ability of one employee to perform several functions at a high level, which are delegated to various tourism specialists, due to a combination of skills, adaptation, and mobility.

There are many classifications of competence in both the local and foreign education systems. Figure 1 contains a classification of personnel competencies in the field of tourism from the works of different authors.

In the process of obtaining higher or secondary specialized education, a graduate in the field of tourism must have elements of professional competence endowed with universal features (Braganca, Costa, Castellucci, Arezes, 2019).

Fig. 1. Classification of personnel competencies in the field of tourism

Such skills include, first of all, analytical, forecasting, information and communication, project forecasting and support, necessary to perform most functions and processes associated with making operational, tactical or strategic decisions in various functional areas of the tourism business.

Paying special attention to the professional training of tourism personnel, it is necessary to ensure a synthesis of scientific and theoretical knowledge with personal qualities that characterize an individual's inclination to certain types of work activities and the success of fulfilling professional duties (Gokalp, Demirors, Eren, 2020).

The analysis of the number of tourists in Uzbekistan in 2019-2022 shows a significant recovery dynamics, although in 2022 this figure lags behind by 15%, the number of rooms compared to 2019 from 26,147 to 33,411, that is, an increase of 7,264 hotel rooms (21.7%).

Among the guests of Uzbekistan, in addition to local tourists and citizens of the country, Russians - 23.4%, Kazakhs - 18.9%, Tajiks - 14.4%, Turks - 7.7%. All foreigners living in hotels: Kyrgyz - 6.3%, Belarusians - 4.6%, Chinese - 3.2%, French - 1.7%.

In the pre-pandemic period of 2019, there were 84,800 foreign citizens, the largest share of which was Russians - 16.8 percent, Kazakhs - 15 percent, Tajiks - 6.3 percent, Chinese - 6.1 percent, Afghans — 5.7 percent, Turks — 5.5 percent.

It is noted that the total number of domestic tourists in the country increased from 8.8 million in 2016 to 14.7 million in 2019 and 15 million in 2021.

Over the past 4 years, 833 new: large, medium and small hotels have been commissioned in Uzbekistan. The total number of placement funds reached 1442. The number of rooms was 33,400, and the number of beds was 71,2.

Fig.2. Infographics: Tourism development in Uzbekistan in 2017-2022

The implementation of the proposed model in practice in the region and other regions specializing in the provision of tourism and recreational services will be successful on the basis of network and cluster interaction between universities, specialized enterprises of the tourism and recreational complex, authorities, research centers and business incubators. Such cooperation will improve the quality of project work and exchange of experience, form a personnel reserve based on predicted directions and scenarios for the development of the tourism sector, and effectively plan personnel development programs.(Fig.2.)

To develop universal competencies of tourism personnel, it is proposed to use certain technologies aimed at continuous development, as well as to develop experience in organizational activities (Bondar, 2011; Charlwood, 2021). One of the foundations of the tourism sector is intercultural communication, which is closely related to the interaction between representatives of different peoples and cultures, thus it is proposed to model the interaction process in order to determine the productivity and unproductivity of communication methods. The analytical abilities of tourism personnel are also very important, as they are aimed at systematizing information and making informed decisions in their professional activities (Bai, 2017). It is necessary to evaluate and adjust the developed universal competencies of tourism personnel in order to increase the efficiency of performing work duties. One of the ways to assess universal competencies is the expert assessment method; this method is complex and difficult to carry out, but still provides the most complete conclusions about the competencies of employees (Pirogova, 2018; (Pirogova, 2018; Gonzalez, Capman, Oswald, Theys , Tomczak, 2019).

The formation of universal competencies is an important problem in the context of innovation and scientific and technological progress of labor duties not only in tourism enterprises. Since the qualifications of a specialist are determined not only by educational diplomas and personal qualities, but also by universal competencies, which are of particular importance at the level of support and service personnel in the field of hospitality and service.

4. Conclusions

Currently, Uzbekistan is fully open for foreign tourists. All restrictions on this have been removed. Positive trends are observed in the rapid recovery of the tourism sector in Uzbekistan, and the above figures indicate that by the end of 2022, up to 4.5 million foreign tourists entered country.

The problem of the formation and development of universal competencies is related to personnel training at the educational level. Universal competencies are a significant tool for an employee's high qualifications, as well as readiness for self-realization and self-development. The formation of universal competencies for work in the field of tourism should occur not only in educational activities, since it is impossible to acquire and master universal competencies only in the process of educational activities. Based on the data obtained on the state of tourism activity in the regions, it follows that the number of hotels and similar accommodation facilities has increased by 15% by 2021, and the need for qualified personnel has increased accordingly.

The most effective model for the formation of universal competencies of tourism personnel will be implemented in the context of network interaction with the involvement of interested business entities and management of the tourism and recreational complex. Practice-oriented experience, transformed by specialists in the process of scientific and teaching activities, conducting master classes and professional tests with students studying in the areas of economics and management in the field of tourism, will be useful.

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